

WP 8.2: SSHOC Certification Support

Use case 2: CTS approach in CESSDA

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Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

The CESSDA Consortium is currently composed of 21 member countries and one observer. Several European countries are in the process of becoming a CESSDA member or observer. CESSDA also has partners in a number of countries outside of the consortium.

Each member state designates one Service Provider so 21 repositories in the ERIC, 10 with CTS.

1. TRUST - CESSDA builds trust in social science research data by ensuring its quality and that it is available for future research. By acquiring the status of a trusted repository, CESSDA Service Providers demonstrate their reliability to researchers as well as national and international research funders. **Statute 7: 'adhere to the principles of the Open Archival Information System reference model and any agreed CESSDA ERIC requirements for operating trusted repositories'; (CTS)**
2. TRAINING
3. TECHNOLOGY
4. TOOLS & SERVICES

CESSDA
TRUST Group

- ❸ The CESSDA Trust Group offers both existing and aspiring Service Providers guidance and support in meeting a range of issues and standards relating to trusted data and services.
- ❸ CESSDA requires the adoption of specific criteria such as the internal obligations required from all members ([CESSDA statutes](#)) and the trustworthy digital repository (TDR) requirements set by the [CoreTrustSeal](#).
- ❸ These goals must be met within the evolving infrastructure (skills, services and technology) of European and international research data science.
- ❸ CESSDA Trust Group consists of a core of Service Providers with experience in trust standards and certification plus key contacts representing each of the CESSDA members and aspiring members.

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TRUST Group

The group's goals are met through:

- 🌀 Guidance, engagement and support to members in understanding, acquiring and maintaining compliance with CESSDA obligations and the requirements of the CoreTrustSeal.
- 🌀 Monitoring and reviewing compliance at an individual and organisational maturity level. Engaging with trust-related elements of the CESSDA work plan including other working groups and projects.
- 🌀 Maintaining an overview of the trust landscape including certification standards and the emergence of the FAIR data principles and the requirements of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

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Activities

- 🌀 Individual contacts with SPs and aspiring SPs
- 🌀 Feedback and advice on trust related matters
- 🌀 Workshops and/or participation in CESSDA activities
- 🌀 Monitoring SPs compliance of the statutes
- 🌀 Participating in relevant groups and projects
- 🌀 Contacts with certification organisations

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Activities

- 🔄 CoreTrustSeal Self-assessment
- 🔄 Internal Peer-review
- 🔄 Comments and recommendations
- 🔄 Repeat as necessary
- 🔄 Apply for CoreTrustSeal

Thank you for your attention!

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<https://www.sshopencloud.eu>

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